

Hand written equation recognition and solution

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Abstract: *Using CNN to create a robust handwritten equation solver is a difficult task in image processing. One of the most difficult challenges in computer vision research is handwritten mathematical expression recognition. The work is made more difficult by the fact that certain characters are segmented and classified. a collection of quadratic equations created by hand This study looks at quadratic equations as well as a single quadratic equation. These equations must be recognized and solved. Horizontal compact projection analysis is used for segmentation. We use both connected component analysis and integrated connected component analysis methodologies. Convolutional Neural Networks Characters are classified using a network. Each appropriate is required for the solution of the problem. Character string operation is used for detection. Finally, the results of the experiment show that the strategy we've described is quite effective. The goal of this project is to create a handwritten alphabet. Equation solver capable of dealing with a wide range of mathematical equations.*

Keywords: *convolutional neural network (CNN), Unified Modelling Language (UML),*

I. INTRODUCTION

Arithmetic is utilized in basically every part of science, including physical science, designing, medication, and financial aspects. The investigation and perception of advanced archives is a critical scholastic subject today. OCR (optical person acknowledgment) can give further developed acknowledgment precision to English characters and digits in electronic books. In the field of PC vision, transcribed numerical articulation acknowledgment stays a troublesome assignment. The amendment pace of image division and acknowledgment can't meet its real prerequisites because of the two-dimensional settling gathering and fluctuated sizes. The initial phase in perceiving numerical articulations is to fragment and arrange the characters. In the field of PC vision, the convolutional neural network (CNN) is one of the most broadly utilized grouping models. Profound Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) inclining has exhibited brilliant execution in the fields of picture grouping, AI, and normal language handling lately. Perceive designs. CNN, most importantly other models, is truly outstanding. UML is a standardized general-purpose modelling language in the field of object-oriented software engineering. The goal is for UML to become a common language for creating models of object-oriented computer software. In its current form UML is comprised of two major components: a Meta-model and a notation. The Unified Modelling Language is a standard language for specifying, Visualization, Constructing and documenting the artefacts of software system, as well as for business modelling and other non-software systems. The UML represents a collection of best engineering practices that have proven successful in the modelling of large and complex systems. The UML is a very important part of developing objects-oriented software and the software development process. The UML uses mostly graphical notations to express the design of software projects.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

To aggregate diverse learners and to train deep architectures are the two principal avenues towards increasing the expressive capabilities of neural networks. Therefore, their combinations merit attention. In this contribution, we study how to apply some conventional diversity methods –bagging and label switching– to a general deep machine, the stacked denoising auto-encoding classifier, in order to solve a number of appropriately selected image recognition problems. The main conclusion of our work is that binarizing multi-class problems is the key to obtain benefit from those diversity methods. Additionally, we check that adding other kinds of performance improvement procedures, such as pre-emphasizing training samples and elastic distortion mechanisms, further increases the quality of the results. In particular, an appropriate combination of all the above methods leads us to reach a new absolute record in classifying MNIST handwritten digits. These facts reveal that there are clear opportunities for designing more powerful classifiers by means of combining different improvement techniques (Alvear et al.,2018). The finite-time synchronization problem of Cohen–Grossberg neural networks (CGNNs) with discontinuous neuron activations and mixed time-delays. Under the extended differential inclusion framework, the famous finite-time stability theorem and generalized Lyapunov approach are used to realize the finite-time synchronization control of drive-response system. Different from the conventional controllers, we propose two classes of novel switching state-feedback controllers which include discontinuous factor sign ($\text{sgn}(\cdot)$) By doing so, the synchronization error of CGNNs can be controlled to converge zero in a finite time. Moreover, we also provide an estimation of the upper bound of

the settling time for synchronization. Finally, two examples and simulation experiment are given to demonstrate the validity of theoretical results (Zuowei Cai et al.,2018). Aim to countermeasure the presentation attack for iris recognition system, an iris liveness detection scheme based on batch normalized convolutional neural network (BNCNN) is proposed to improve the reliability of the iris authentication system. The BNCNN architecture with eighteen layers is constructed to detect the genuine iris and fake iris, including convolutional layer, batch-normalized (BN) layer, Relu layer, pooling layer and full connected layer. The iris image is first pre-processed by iris segmentation and is normalized to 256×256 pixels, and then the iris features are extracted by BNCNN. With these features, the genuine iris and fake iris are determined by the decision-making layer. Batch normalization technique is used in BNCNN to avoid the problem of over fitting and gradient disappearing during training. Extensive experiments are conducted on three classical databases: the CASIA Iris Lamp database, the CASIA Iris Syn database and Ndcontact database. The results show that the proposed method can effectively extract micro texture features of the iris, and achieve higher detection accuracy compared with some typical iris liveness detection methods. (Long et al.,2019)

III. METHODOLOGY

Handwritten mathematical expression recognition is one of the most challenging problems in computer vision research. The goal of this project is to create handwritten Mathematical expressions. The segmentation and classification of some features. both many quadratic equations and a single quadratic equation are examined. They need to be identified and solved. For segmentation, horizontal compact projection analysis is performed. We employ both integrated connected component analysis and connected component analysis. Neural networks with convolutions A network are used to classify characters. Each proper step is necessary to solve the issue. For detection, character string operation is employed. The mathematical expression should be able to be processed beforehand by the system. Both the language and the mathematical symbols in the image should be recognized by the system. A penmanship acknowledgment framework's objective is to make an interpretation of manually written characters into designs that are machine meaningful. Vehicle tag recognizable proof, postal letter arranging, check truncation framework (CTS) checking and recorded report conservation in archaeological divisions, old archive robotization in libraries and banks, and different applications are among the generally normal. These fields manage enormous information bases, requiring fantastic acknowledgment precision, diminished processing intricacy, and predictable acknowledgment framework execution. Profound neural models are supposed to be more invaluable than shallow neural models. A convolutional neural organization is a type of profound neural network with applications in picture grouping, object acknowledgment, proposal frameworks, signal handling, normal language handling, PC vision, and face acknowledgment, among others. They are more proficient than their archetypes (Multi-layer perceptron (MLP), and so on) in light of the fact that they can consequently perceive the fundamental parts of a thing (here an item can be a picture, a written by hand character, a face, and so on) without any human oversight or collaboration. An exceptionally proficient CNN is the result of progressive component learning's solid abilities. A use case diagram in the Unified Modeling Language (UML) is a type of behavioral diagram defined by and created from a Use-case analysis. Its purpose is to present a graphical overview of the functionality provided by a system in terms of actors, their goals (represented as use cases), and any dependencies between those use cases. The main purpose of a use case diagram is to show what system functions are performed for which actor. Roles of the actors in the system can be depicted.

The class diagram is used to refine the use case diagram and define a detailed design of the system. The class diagram classifies the actors defined in the use case diagram into a set of interrelated classes. The relationship or association between the classes can be either an "is-a" or "has-a" relationship. Each class in the class diagram may be capable of providing certain functionalities. These functionalities provided by the class are termed "methods" of the class. Apart from this, each class may have certain "attributes" that uniquely identify the class. The process flows in the system are captured in the activity diagram. Similar to a state diagram, an activity diagram also consists of activities, actions, transitions, initial and final states, and guard conditions.

- User signup: Using this module user will get register
- User signin: Using this module user will login into the application
- Build CNN model: using this module algorithm will generate

CNN: A Convolutional Neural Network, also known as CNN or ConvNet, is a class of neural networks that specializes in processing data that has a grid-like topology, such as an image. A digital image is a binary representation of visual data. It contains a series of pixels arranged in a grid-like fashion that contains pixel values to denote how bright and what color each pixel should be. The human brain processes a huge amount of information the second we see an image. Each neuron works in its own receptive field and is connected to other neurons in a way that they cover the entire visual field. Just as each neuron responds to stimuli only in the restricted region of the visual field called the receptive field in the biological vision system, each neuron in a CNN processes data only in its receptive field as well. The layers are arranged in such a way so that they detect simpler patterns first (lines, curves, etc.) and more complex patterns (faces, objects, etc.) further along. By using a CNN, one can enable sight to computers.

The technologies used are python, TensorFlow, NumPy, Pandas, Matplotlib, Scikit – learn.

Static Testing is performed without actually running the developing product. Basically, such desk-checking is required to detect bugs and issues that are present in the code itself. Such a check-up is important at the pre-deployment stage as it helps avoid problems caused by errors in the code and software structure deficits. Structural testing, also known as white-box testing, is required to detect and fix bugs and errors emerging during the preproduction stage of the software development process. At this stage, unit testing based on the software structure is performed using regression testing. In most cases, it is an automated process working within the test automation framework to speed up the development process at this stage. Developers and QA engineers have full access to the software’s structure and data flows (data flows testing), so they could track any changes (mutation testing) in the system’s behaviour by comparing the tests’ outcomes with the results of previous iterations (control flow testing). The final stage of testing focuses on the software’s reactions to various activities rather than on the mechanisms behind these reactions. In other words, behavioural testing, also known as Blackbox testing, presupposes running numerous tests, mostly manual, to see the product from the user’s point of view. QA engineers usually have some specific information about a business or other purpose of the software (‘the black box’) to run usability tests, for example, and react to bugs as regular users of the product will do. Behavioural testing also may include automation (regression tests) to eliminate human error if repetitive activities are required. For example, you may need to fill 100 registration forms on the website to see how the product copes with such an activity, so the automation of this test is preferable.

Figure.6: Static Testing

Figure. 7 Black box testing

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure.8 Sign in Page

Figure.9 Written Equation

Figure.10 Choose file

Figure.11 Choose file for extract data

Figure 15 Final Output

IV. CONCLUSION

The focal point of this review was on perceiving manually written numerical quadratics. For acknowledgment, we think about single quadratics just as series of quadratics. Examine projections Each line of quadratics is fragmented utilizing a particular minimized flat projection. For character division, an associated part with a high achievement rate is utilized. For image acknowledgment like '=', which is a solitary image blended in with two separate associated parts, a further developed form of associated part is used. The most troublesome part of arrangement is highlights extraction. Besides, penmanship is more diligently to recognize on the grounds that to a few preset highlights. After effectively perceiving quadratics in any mix, we process the found condition to get the quadratics' answer. We use a string activity way to deal with get the worth of a, b, and c of every quadratic of the structure $ay^2+by+c=0$ in this segment. At long last, we accomplished best in class execution in both the discovery and arrangement stages.

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